

AN OVERVIEW OF THE NUMBER NINE FRACTURE

Smrithi Srinivasan¹

Post-Graduate, Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, MR Ambedkar Dental College and Hospital, Bangalore, India

Correspondence: drsmrithi1@gmail.com

OVERVIEW

ABSTRACT: *Ellis Class IX fracture is designated to trauma to the primary dentition. This audio transcript emphasises on the impact of dental trauma in children and the factors that influence treatment aspects.*

Keywords: *Primary teeth, Pediatric Dentistry, Dental Fear*

How to cite: Srinivasan S. An overview on the number nine fracture. *The Quadrant*. 2023;2(1):4.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11121195>

Sir,

Ellis Class IX fracture, or trauma to the primary dentition is a common occurrence in children. A recent international study on traumatic dental injuries involving primary teeth revealed a worldwide prevalence of 22.7%. Unintentional falls, collisions and leisure activities are the most common reasons for traumatic dental injuries, as it is typical for toddlers to crawl, stagger and fall before being able to walk as part of their development.¹

Anterior teeth are the most commonly injured, particularly the central and lateral incisors. A traumatic dental injury could be the child's first visit to the dentist, which can prove to be challenging for the child due to fear and lack of understanding. Therefore, we should attempt to minimize the child's anxiety. Hence, it is essential to adopt a structured and organized approach, connect a complete clinical history, examination, investigations, and provide treatment options.

Given the consequences of traumatic dental injuries on the child and the developing permanent dentition, there is a need to educate parents, teachers, and health care professionals about the need for dental assessment and the initial first aid management for dramatic dental injuries to the primary dentition.

REFERENCE

1. Elleray E, Brizuela M, Pepper T. Trauma to the Primary Dentition. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; June 1, 2023.

